

Guidebook Depositing Restricted Access In The DANS Data Stations

Version 1.0

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Document Information

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Citation and reuse information

Licence of this document: CC-BY 4.0

Version: 1.0

Date: 27-03-2023

This document is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887484>

This guidebook was created amongst others to support the archiving process of data collected in the [COORDINATE project](#) funded by the European Commission under Grant agreement ID: 101008589. In addition, members from the [ODISSEI](#) FAIR Support team have provided input to the guide.

Contents

INTRODUCTION	4
ACCESS CATEGORIES AND LICENCES IN THE DANS DATA STATIONS	6
AVAILABLE LICENCES.....	7
CREATING A DATA ACCESS PROTOCOL FOR YOUR DATASET	8
<i>General information</i>	8
<i>Information about reuse restrictions</i>	8
<i>Information about the processing of access requests</i>	9
SPECIFYING DATA ACCESS CONDITIONS IN THE DANS DATA STATIONS	10
DATA ACCESS PROTOCOL TEMPLATE	12
REFERENCES AND FURTHER READING	15
INFORMATION ABOUT DANS SERVICES.....	15
MANUALS AND GUIDANCE	15
OTHER REFERENCES.....	15
APPENDIX 1	16
SELECTING THE RIGHT ACCESS CATEGORY FOR YOUR DATASET.....	16

Introduction

This guidebook is meant for anyone who considers depositing data in one of the **DANS Data Stations**¹. The guidebook outlines the possibilities that DANS offers to deposit data under open and restricted access. It provides guidance for you - the depositor - who chooses to publish data with restricted access, explaining what to consider and how to create a data access protocol.

The DANS Data Stations are digital repositories in which individual researchers or organizations can deposit data to store them safely for the long term and to make them reusable for others. DANS hosts four domain-specific Data Stations, which are tailored to the needs of specific research communities:

- [Archaeology](#)
- [Social Sciences and Humanities \(SSH\)](#)
- [Life Sciences \(LS\)](#)
- [Physical and Technical sciences.](#)

In particular in the SSH and LS domain, many researchers work with data that contain **personal information** or which are **sensitive** in some way. These types of data can often not be shared openly, but require some **restrictions** and management of the access.

This document outlines the options that DANS offers to restrict access to datasets and provides advice on how you can manage data access after you have published your data with DANS.

We first provide more information about the **access categories** and **licences** that DANS offers as well as giving advice on how to choose the suitable category.

Then we focus on the creation of a **Data Access Protocol** that should be established when data is stored under restricted access. We outline the kind of information that the protocol should cover, and we provide questions that guide you in collecting this information.

This guidebook also contains a **template** Data Access Protocol that depositors are anyone to use when depositing under restricted access in the DANS Data Stations.

Finally, we provide a list of references and interesting documents for further reading on this topic.

¹ This document focuses our service around the DANS Data Stations. DANS also offers DataverseNL and our DANS Data Vault which are not discussed in this document but for which you can find more information on our website: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-services/dataversenl/> and <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-services/data-vault/>

We hope that after reading this document, you feel confident to prepare a data access protocol for datasets that you want to publish restricted access. Such a protocol should specify the access conditions and how requests will be assessed. In that way you and your research team can manage the process as best as possible, and the process is fully transparent to repository users who want to access the data.

This guidebook was created in part to support the discussions around the deposit of datasets collected within COORDINATE, a European project which aims to facilitate improved access to survey data on child wellbeing. As data on child wellbeing may contain sensitive information, restricted access can often be the preferred form of publication. Hence having guidance on how to prepare a data access protocol to manage access requests is a crucial ingredient in ensuring availability and access to this valuable data.

Access Categories and Licences in the DANS Data Stations

When depositing data in one of the Data Stations you have two options: You can publish your data files with **open access**, or you can publish them with **restricted access**. Depending on the access category that you chose, you will need to select a suitable licence that specifies the conditions of reuse. In this guidebook, we first discuss the two access categories that can be applied to a deposit and then outline the licences depositors can choose. The rest of the guidebook assumes that you want to publish your data under restricted access but if you are unsure which access category fits best, Appendix 1 provides more information on choosing the right access category for your dataset.

Open access

When publishing **open access**, anyone can download the data files after accepting the [Terms of Use](#) of the Data Station. After your data files have been published, there are no actions needed from your side. Users can download the data files without logging into the Data Station.

Access categories are selected **per file**, so two files in one dataset can have different access categories. You can have a deposit where some files are openly available, and some files are restricted.

Restricted access

When publishing **restricted access** and enabling access requests³, a user can download the files only after you have given permission. A user needs to log into the Data Station, accepting the [Terms of Use](#), and then needs to submit an access request. You as the depositor - or someone that you mandate - will need to evaluate the request in the interface of the Data Station. When you have granted the request, the requester can download the data files.

For both open and restricted access data files, an **embargo** can be set. Setting an embargo means that the data is unavailable until a certain amount of time has passed².

² An Embargo can be an important tool, for instance when a publication based on the deposited data still has to appear, or when research has been carried out in a consortium which has agreed upon such an embargo period.

³ It should be noted that it is possible to set data files within a dataset to restricted access without enabling an access request. In this case no one will be able to access your data files. Since this manual focuses on data that are deposited at DANS for reuse, we will not further discuss this option in this document.

As the depositor, you are responsible for assessing whether the data you hold can be published with open or restricted access in a DANS Data Station. There are cases in which restricting access and applying a licence is not considered sufficient protection. For certain types of (sensitive) data it can be the case, for instance, that a secure environment is needed for the analysis, or that the resulting outputs need to be checked and verified against certain criteria before they can be published, or that you require the destruction of the data directly after use. This is not something that our Data Stations currently offer. However, we plan to assess our systems to allow for archiving of these more sensitive types of data in the future. It may then be possible to deposit sensitive data at DANS and allow data to be transferred into secure environments where they can safely be reused.

This guidebook for the time being concerns itself with the current restricted access category of our Data Stations, where users are able to download data after permission has been granted.

Available licences

DANS offers different licences for open and restricted access datasets. For open datasets, DANS encourages the use of [CC0 1.0](#) or [CC-BY 4.0](#), but other licences are available as well as outlined [on our website](#).

It should be noted that a licence is selected for the entire dataset, not at the level of individual data files. For datasets which contain restricted access files, the depositor should always select the [DANS Licence](#), which was specifically designed for restricted access data. It can be the case that the dataset also contains files which are openly available, these files can be downloaded freely but the selected DANS Licence will apply to all the files.

The DANS Licence, amongst other things, specifies that the user of the data needs to act in accordance with the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, the GDPR, and other applicable laws and regulations. It also states that the user should cite the dataset, and that data may not be distributed further without permission from the depositor.

Creating a Data Access Protocol for your dataset

For all restricted access datasets, we recommend the creation of a **Data Access Protocol** (DAP) that holds all the relevant information you need to process access requests.

The DAP can be stored as part of your Data Management Plan (DMP), and it is useful to share the DAP with anyone involved in the project so that they are aware of the agreements that have been made and the criteria under which access will be given.

As stated in our [Terms of Use](#) and our [Data Stations Policy](#), DANS requires depositors to process requests for data in a reasonable time period. A DAP can be helpful to ensure a smooth process as it encourages you to specify responsibilities for the processing of requests and also asks to provide alternative contact details. Moreover, if in the future another person or organization would be assigned to take over the management of the data and process requests, the DAP can provide guidance for them on how requests should be handled and evaluated.

The following sections describe how you can structure your DAP and what information should be provided in each part.

General information

The DAP should start with general information about the dataset it refers to. If you deposit multiple datasets for which the same procedure is followed you can summarize this in one DAP. The information that is provided includes basic details such as the date, name of the depositor and the DOI(s) of the dataset(s) the DAP concerns. If you provide the DOI(s), basic metadata of the datasets can easily be accessed, and you don't need to provide this information again yourself in the form.

Information about reuse restrictions

In this section of the DAP, you should specify any restrictions you have for others to reuse the data. This can concern the **purpose of reuse** (e.g. not allowing commercial use, allowing use for research purposes only) or the **person reusing** the data (e.g. limiting this to certain professions or regions). You should also specify if you require a written description of **motivation** from the requester and if so what this should contain and how you evaluate the motivation letter. It is also useful to note whether

additional conditions apply (besides the Terms of Use of the Data Station and the DANS Licence which users have already accepted). Finally, you should also specify if **costs** apply for reuse or if reuse is limited to a **specific time period**.

When considering all of the above we encourage you to make data available with the Open Science principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” in mind. Consider what you need to know from the person who wants to reuse the data in order to comply with ethical and legal requirements and try to avoid asking more. Following the Open Science principles asks us to only apply restrictions when necessary to protect data.

Information about the processing of access requests

In the last section of the DAP, you should specify **who** is processing the requests and how they can be **contacted**. It is good to consider if an individual will be responsible for the processing or if you want to work with a team of people - in some cases you may want to establish a **Data Access Committee (DAC)**⁴.

Some depositors process requests through a general email address if the requests are handled by a team of data managers or data stewards. If requests are processed by an individual using an institutional account, you need to make sure you contact DANS in case you change institutions so that the rights to manage the access requests can be transferred in time⁵.

To ensure access to the data for the long term, we also ask you to consider how requests will be handled if this initial person or team is not available (e.g. due to vacation, illness, or other absences) and provide **alternative contact details**. Lastly, it is good to consider what **response time** you can guarantee for handling requests. DANS encourages depositors to respond as soon as possible but requires that requests are processed within three months.

⁴ Data Access Committees are more commonly established in the field of health and medical sciences. This paper makes suggestions about a framework under which DACs should operate, how they should be organised, and how to constitute them in the medical field <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-020-0453-z>

⁵ Our [FAQ](#) contains information about the transfer of rights to other user accounts.

Specifying Data Access Conditions in the DANS Data Stations

Having the DAP filled in before you deposit your datafiles in DANS will help you to fill out the metadata in the “Terms” field of the Data Station. You can follow our [deposit manual](#) which outlines how to upload datafiles, selecting the licence and restricting the access to individual or all files. The “Terms” section of the metadata can then be used to provide information about the process of data access.

Providing this information helps a user to assess beforehand if they are eligible to access the data and what they need to consider before submitting a request.

This ensures that the user is well informed before they use the “Request Access” button in the Data Station interface to request access for your dataset.

The table below gives an overview of the fields in the “Terms” section of the metadata that we recommend you to fill out⁶. The information you should provide is already part of your DAP so you can easily copy it from there into the metadata in the DANS Data Station.

Dataset Terms	
Licence/Data Use Agreement	DANS Licence should be selected
Restricted files + Terms of Access	
Request Access	“Enable access request” box should be ticked ⁷ .
Terms of Access for Restricted Files	Provide here the information that is specified under “Information about reuse restrictions” in your DAP
Availability Status	If there is a restriction on the availability, this can be stated here. For instance, you may have an embargo period.
Contact for Access	If the contact person for the data access is different from the email address associated with the depositor, you can specify

⁶ There are other additional fields in this section (Data Access Place, Original Archive, Size of Collection, Study Completion) that you can complete if they are applicable in your case. They are not obligatory or recommended as they do not apply in most cases and are thus not further discussed here.

⁷ If the box “Enable access request” is not ticked no one will be able to access the datafiles as no one will be allowed to submit an access request.

	the contact details here. Otherwise you can leave this field empty.
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Data Access Protocol Template

You can use the template designed here to summarize all the information that will be helpful for processing data requests. If you submit a datasets with restricted access to DANS, we would like to receive a copy of this Data Access Protocol. Note that an editable version of this template is also available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887571>.

As the DAP contains very relevant information about the access to the data, we recommend that the DAP is written in such a way that it can be openly shared (i.e. so that it does not contain any sensitive information).

General information	
Date	
Name of Depositor	
DOIs of datasets this form applies to	
If available include a link to a related Data Management Plan	
Information about restrictions for data reuse	
Do you allow data to be used for other purposes than research? [Yes] [No]	
Room to elaborate	
Do you allow students to use your data? [Yes] [No]	
Room to elaborate	
Do you allow teachers to use your data for teaching? [Yes] [No]	
Room to elaborate	
Is use limited to certain organisations or individuals? [Yes] [No]	
Room to elaborate	

Do you allow use for commercial purposes? [Yes] [No]	
Room to elaborate	
Is use limited to certain regions? [Yes] [No] <i>For instance state if data needs to remain in the EU or in the Netherlands</i>	
Room to elaborate <i>Please indicate why you apply certain regional limitations.</i>	
Do you require a written motivation from the requester? [Yes] [No]	
If yes, please specify: What information do you expect in the motivation letter? Do you expect a certain format or length? What are the criteria you use to evaluate the motivation letter?	
Is there a time period for which this protocol applies? <i>In some cases data can be made openly available after a given time period.</i>	
Are there other agreements that the requester has to sign to gain access to the data?	
Are there costs associated with the use of the data?	
Information about the processing of access requests	
Which individuals or institutes are allowed to decide about the requests? <i>Do you establish a Data Access Committee (DAC) or will one person handle the requests?</i>	
Who will be responsible for granting or rejecting access requests? <i>Please provide at least one name and email address</i>	

What happens if the person responsible is no longer able to perform this task? <i>Please provide name and email of an alternative contact</i>	
What response time can you guarantee for handling requests?	
Other information	
Room for any additional information	

References and further reading

Information about DANS Services

- The DANS Data Stations <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/> [Accessed 22-11-2023]
- DANS Data Stations Policy: <https://dans.knaw.nl/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/DANS-Data-Stations-Policy.pdf> [Accessed 22-11-2023]
- DANS Data Stations Terms of Use: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/legal/terms-and-conditions-data-stations/> [Accessed 22-11-2023]
- DataverseNL <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-services/dataversen/> [Accessed 22-11-2023]
- The DANS Data Vault: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-services/data-vault/> [Accessed 22-11-2023]

Manuals and Guidance

- DANS Manual for depositing data: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/depositing-data-manual/> [Accessed 22-11-2023]
- Frequently Asked Questions about the DANS Data Stations <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/faq/> [Accessed 22-11-2023]
- CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide (DMEG): <https://dmeg.CESSDA.eu/> [Accessed 22-11-2023]

Other references

- Cheah, P.Y., Piasecki, J. Data Access Committees. *BMC Med Ethics* 21, 12 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-020-0453-z>
- Verburg, M., Braukmann, R., & Mahabier, W. (2023). Making Qualitative Data Reusable - A Short Guidebook For Researchers And Data Stewards Working With Qualitative Data (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8160880>
- Verburg, M., Braukmann, R., & Mahabier, W. (2023). Decision Tree - Making Qualitative Data Reusable (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8160890>

Appendix 1

Selecting the right access category for your dataset

When you want to deposit your dataset in a DANS Data Station, you need to decide which access category is most suitable for your dataset.

DANS promotes the principle **“As open as possible, as closed as necessary”**. In our view, access should only be restricted when it is legally or ethically necessary to do so. In most cases reasons to restrict access have to do with personal data or sensitive information in the data files.

The table below gives some indications under which circumstances one would publish Open Access versus Restricted Access. The decision is made by you, the depositor, and often your local institution provides guidance through the data stewards and privacy officers.

When to publish Open Access	When to publish Restricted Access
There is no personal data in the data or personal data has been anonymized. The dataset does not contain any sensitive information.	The dataset contains personal data that cannot be anonymized or pseudonymized.
Personal data has been pseudonymized and you have gained informed consent from the participants to share the pseudonymized data without restrictions. The dataset does not contain any sensitive information.	Your consent form specifies that the reuse of the data is restricted in certain ways.
You have gained informed consent from participants to share personal data without restrictions. The dataset does not contain any sensitive information.	You need to know who is re-using your data.
	You need to ensure your data is reused for specific purposes only.
	The dataset contains sensitive information.

DANS has published [a guidebook](#) and [decision tree](#) with which the access options for qualitative data can be assessed. As outlined in this decision tree and in the table above, data can typically be published openly when it is not sensitive and when no personal information is present. In addition, if personal information can be anonymized or if full consent has been provided by the research participants, open

access may also be an option. In the latter case, the research participants need to be fully aware that they give consent to disseminate their personal information without any restriction. This must be stated explicitly in the consent form.

Restricted access is often chosen when personal data cannot be anonymized or when the informed consent requires some form of restriction. Restricted access can also be applicable when the depositor wants to ensure that data is being used for a specific purpose or by a specific group of people (e.g. by scientific staff from academic institutions). Restricted access can therefore be used for datasets which contain somewhat sensitive information as it allows the depositor to evaluate the individuals who reuse the data. It needs to be emphasised, however, that restricted access datafiles will be downloaded by the user after permission has been granted, so you need to ensure that that is permissible given the sensitivity of your dataset.

If after considering these aspects you conclude that you can best publish **Open Access**, you can follow our [deposit manual](#) to upload your datasets and no more preparations regarding Data Access Protocols are needed.

- If after considering these aspects you conclude that you can best publish **Restricted Access**, you need to gather some information for a Data Access Protocol which is outlined in the above sections of this guide.